

Identifying Common Errors in Vertical Lowercase Manuscript Writing of the First Graders in Primary School

Muhammet Fatih Doğan¹

Zeynep Doğan²

^{1,2}Yıldız Technical University, Department of Primary Education, Istanbul, Turkey

¹Email: mfdogan@yildiz.edu.tr

²Email: zeynepyildiz.2005@hotmail.com

(Corresponding Author)

Abstract

The aim of the study is to identify common writing errors of the first graders in primary school. The sample of study was consisted of 67 students. Case study was used for the research design. A data collection tool was developed for identifying the errors that students have made while writing vertical lowercase letters. According to the findings, the most common types of errors encountered occurred as a result of non-compliance with the rules related to the writing directions of the lowercase letters. Also, it was seen that curved shaped were drawn in some letters which must have been drawn a line-shaped, that some letters were drawn round not fully closed which must have been drawn round, that the round of letters were drawn as ellipses that when the letters were drawn ellipse-shaped letters were drawn in a tilted way and that the round of letters was combined with the line in the wrong side.

Keywords: Primary school, Writing errors, Vertical lowercase letters.

Citation | Muhammet Fatih Doğan; Zeynep Doğan (2018). Identifying Common Errors in Vertical Lowercase Manuscript Writing of the First Graders in Primary School. Journal of Education and e-Learning Research, 5(3): 144-156.

History:

Received: 5 March 2018

Revised: 14 June 2018

Accepted: 20 August 2018

Published: 9 October 2018

Licensed: This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Attribution 3.0 License

Publisher: Asian Online Journal Publishing Group

Contribution/Acknowledgement: Both authors contributed to the conception and design of the study.

Funding: This study received no specific financial support.

Competing Interests: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interests.

Transparency: The authors confirm that the manuscript is an honest, accurate, and transparent account of the study was reported; that no vital features of the study have been omitted; and that any discrepancies from the study as planned have been explained.

Ethical: This study follows all ethical practices during writing.

Contents

1. Introduction	145
2. Method	145
3. Findings	146
4. Discussion	155
5. Conclusion	156
References	156

1. Introduction

In developed societies, the progress of an individual in his/her field is only possible if he/she has advanced reading and writing skills. Because modern people cannot have the necessary level of knowledge without having an effective reading skill. Similarly, an individual cannot share his knowledge with his environment without gaining an effective writing skill (Sahin, 2012). It is acknowledged that education is very instrumental and an essential agent in national development. Akdemir and Eyerci (2016) as a result, improving the quality of education, especially at the basic education level, has become the concern of all nations (Esia-Donkoh and Baffoe, 2018). Kaya and Akdemir (2016) education is a condition which can alter a person's values and can influence the changes in a person's behaviors (Istiningsih, 2016). No doubt, the acquisition of literacy skills is seen as the primary goal of basic education (Sahin, 2012). Writing is to be able to produce the symbols and signs necessary to express our thoughts systematically (Akyol, 2001). Writing is the written form of expressing feelings, thoughts and information in the mind. Writing helps individuals to learn as well as meet their communication needs (Belet and Yaşar, 2007). When the definitions related to writing are examined, it is seen that the general goal of writing is to express thoughts through writing (Sahin, 2012).

The text is defined as the forms of words and phrases in the spoken language identified on paper by some symbolic figures and drawings (Celenk, 2007). Handwriting is one of the most important skills that must be earned in primary school education. The acquisition of handwriting begins with first reading and writing process (Göğüş, 1982). The studies to be carried out on the issue and the methods to be applied are included in the primary school Turkish programs (Ministry of National Education, 1997).

In primary school programs of our country until 2005, the use of vertical letters in the teaching of uppercase and lowercase alphabet was requested. The adjoining oblique writing instruction was handled together with the "sound based sentence method" in the 2005 Primary School Turkish Language Teaching Program (Grades 1th-5th) and it was envisaged to teach the adjacent oblique writing to the students in the first grade of primary education and to continue this writing in the later years (Sahin, 2012). With the Turkish Language Course Teaching Program (for 1th-8th Grades) which was started to be implemented in the 2017-2018 academic year, the adjacent oblique letters in the Turkish first reading and writing instruction were replaced by the vertical alphabet (MoNE, 2018).

Ayık and Ataş-Akdemir (2016) writing skill is a skill gained with practice. Developing students' writing skills depends on continuous reading, writing, and analyzing their own writings. The first grade of primary school is very crucial because of gaining the necessary skills. Teacher should correct learning errors in students' writings with appropriate educational way considering of the student's developmental level (Demirel, 2006). In primary school, primary school teachers need to determine the characteristics of students' writing mistakes in order to correct their writing errors. Errors frequently made by students in writing in Turkish programs are listed as the direction of writing, the size of writing, writing on the line border, spacing between words, the writing style of letters and clearness of writing (Bay, 2010).

When the literature review was investigated, there was no study found about what kind of mistakes were made in the manuscript writing of the vertical lowercase letters. Therefore, the errors related to the "way of writing letters", which is one of the mistakes that primary school students often make during primary school writing studies, have been examined in the study. Another reason why such a study is needed is that mistakes are found regarding letters and numbers when the writing of students from 2nd, 3rd and 4th grades at primary school are analyzed. It is thought that this study is especially important in order to be aware of the possible errors that may occur in the students and to prevent these errors from occurring while performing the reading and writing processes of the primary school teachers who are new to the profession.

Considering of the topic, "What are the mistakes made by primary school students about the manuscript writing of the vertical letters?" has been determined as the problem of the study.

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

Case study from qualitative research methods was used in the study. According to Stake (1995) and Yin (2009;2012) case study is a research design in which researchers analyze a particular situation, often a program, event, action, process, one or more individuals in depth. In the study, research design was determined as case study as the vertical letters of the first graders in primary school were examined and their learning errors were tried to be analyzed.

2.2. Participants

The research was carried out with 67 students studying in first grade in public school. The reason why first graders were preferred was that first grade is the expected year for students to acquire their reading and writing skills. It is thought that a positive contribution can be made to the acquisition of reading and writing skills through investigating of the situation in the process. It is thought that measures can be taken to eliminate these errors by determining the ongoing errors.

2.3. Data Collection Instruments

In the study, the data collection instrument was developed by the researchers in order to determine the first graders' writing errors on vertical letters. When developing a data collection instrument, 12 objects and animals were identified, all of the 29 letters in the alphabet will be found at least once and students encountered in daily life. At this stage sound groups in the curriculum are taken into consideration. Then, some words were chosen and these words were deve (camel), gözlük (glasses), jilet (razor), kamyon (truck), köpek (dog), yıldız (star), bisiklet (bisiklet), fare (mouse), ağaç (tree), cami (Mosque), hortum (hose) and kuş (bird). The images expressing these words were placed on A4 appropriately, leaving a space under each visual for the name of the visual. Figure 1 shows a visual example of a part of the data collection instrument for letters.

Figure-1. A part of the data collection instrument for letter typing mistakes.

Source: Data Collection Instrument

After the data collection instruments were developed, three classroom teachers and three experts were consulted. As a result, the data collection tools are finalized and ready for implementation.

2.4. Data Collection and Data Analysis

The data collection instrument was given to students and the names of visuals were asked to be written in lowercase letters. After the data collection instruments were distributed to the students, 40 minutes were given and they were asked to fill the gaps appropriately.

Collected data were generally examined and papers that were unreadable, the majority of papers which were not filled in or filled with improper content were excluded from the evaluation.

In the review process, the data obtained from the students were compared with the correct spelling patterns of lower case letters (Figure 2), and especially common mistakes made were classified.

Figure-2. Writing of vertical basic lowercase letters

Source: MoNE (2018)

3. Findings

In this section, types of common errors that students make when writing vertical lowercase letters and sample visuals from each type of error is tabulated.

Table-1. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letter “a”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
a	Round part of the letter is not a proper round, round is not closed completely	
	Writing the letter in oblique	
	Drawing the vertical line too thick	
	Drawing the vertical line completely outside of the circle or not drawing the vertical line	
	Drawing vertical line in/out of the circle	
	Drawing line in an oblique way instead of straight line	
	Drawing lower and upper side of the vertical line very short/long	

Source: Research Data

Table-2. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letter “b”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
b	The shape of the round is not done properly as a result of the space of the upper/lower part of the area that is in contact with the line remains blank	
	Distorted round shape (ellipse shaped and/or inclined, angled round etc.)	
	Drawing the round too big/small	
	Drawing the vertical line disproportionately	
	Drawing the vertical line curved/ oblique	
	Writing the letter reversely	

Source: Research Data

Table-3. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letters “c” and “ç”

Letters	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
c and ç	Drawing the lower / upper of the curve longer / shorter	
	Drawing the lower / upper tip of the curve inward	
	Drawing the tip portions of the curve outward	
	Forked construction of the tip parts of the curve	
	Drawing the curve in a cornered way	
	Drawing the letter in oblique	
	Sketching the curve itself jaggedly	

Source: Research Data

Table-4. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the bottom part of letter “ç”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
The bottom part of letter “ç”	Not centered (right bottom or left bottom)	
	Making a lot of space between the letter and its bottom line	
	Drawing the letter with its bottom line adjoined	
	Drawing a circle in the bottom of letter and filling in	
	Drawing a curve line but not a straight line	
	Passing the bottom part through the letter	

Source: Research Data

Table-5. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letter “d”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
d	The round is not drawn properly	
	Have crossed the vertical line several times	
	Round and vertical line in the wrong place to merge (near the bottom end of the line to merge in place)	
	Overhang on lower end of vertical line	
	Using only one curve instead of a vertical line and a round need to be done	
	Inclined drawing of vertical line	
	drawing vertical line and/or round improperly, drawing several times over the round	
	Drawing the vertical line too long	
	Vertical line without protruded at lower end	

Source: Research Data

Table-6. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letter “e”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
e	Overflow of horizontal line from left	
	The left tip of the horizontal line does not touch the circular part	
	The horizontal line and the top of the circular segment are very close together, there is no upper space or very little	
	Drawing cornered instead of circular line	
	The circular part is not drawn properly / the letter appears thin	
	The lower tip is too long/short	
	Drawing of horizontal line inclined / crooked drawing	

Source: Research Data

Table-7. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letter “f”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
f	Involuted drawing of the lower tip	
	Horizontal line not positioned correctly (very up / right middle / or below)	
	Unclear upper tip	
	Crossing the vertical line several times	
	The occurrence of protrusion in the upper part of the letter because of not to follow the spelling rule.	
	Drawing the letter italic	
	Drawing of horizontal line too long / too short / oblique / curve	

Source: Research Data

Table-8. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letters “g” and “ğ”

Letters	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
g and ğ	Make the round improperly	
	The top of the letter is not done / exaggerated	
	Drawing the round unclosed completely	
	Drawing the tail part too short/too long	
	Inadequate / very curved tail	
	Finding deformities because the spelling rules of the letter are not obeyed	

Source: Research Data

Table-9. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the top part of letter “ğ”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
The top part of letter “ğ”	Making the top part straight line / slash line	
	Creating a curve shape of the top part	
	Drawing Adjacent to the bottom part of the top part	
	Exaggeration of the curve of the upper part	

Source: Research Data

Table-10. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letter “h”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
h	Drawing vertical line as curve or oblique	
	The curve line is not drawn properly	
	One of the lower tips is short and the other one is long	
	Drawing several times on the letter	
	Shape deformity / gaps because of incorrect letter drawing direction	
	Drawing the vertical line very short/very long	

Source: Research Data

Table-11. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letters “ı” and “i”

Letters	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
ı and i	Too short/too long drawing / unable to set type size	
	Drawing as an oblique / a curved line	
	Drawing over several times	
	Curvilinear drawing of lower / upper tip	

Source: Research Data

Table-12. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the top part of letter “i”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
The top part of letter “i”	Not to make upper part in the middle (upper left / upper right)	
	Drawing the upper part very long	
	Making the upper part as a point	
	Making the upper part as a circle	
	Making the upper part as a curve	
	Drawing the upper part in two separate pieces	

Source: Research Data

Table-13. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letter “j”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
j	Drawing the vertical line as a curve	
	Drawing the letter italic	
	Not to draw upper part	
	Writing the letter reversely	
	The upper part is made as a point / round / as a very long line / as a curve	
	Drawing tail part non-curvature/less curvature	
	Making the tail part very curved	
	Making the tail part very cornered	
	Drawing the letter for several times	
	Too long / too short length	

Source: Research Data

Table-14. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letter “k”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
k	Drawing vertical line as a curve / oblique	
	Drawing vertical line too long / short	
	Curve drawing of Diagonal sections	
	Finding a space where the diagonal parts should be joined with the vertical line	
	Drawing protrusion where the diagonal parts need to be joined with the vertical line	
	Drawing diagonal parts too long/short.	
	Making Diagonal parts very close/far to each other	
	joining in the very bottom / right middle / above the center instead the diagonal sections need to be joined slightly below the center line with the vertical line	

Source: Research Data

Table-15. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letter “l”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
l	Drawing the letter height too long/too short	
	Drawing the letter vertical line in oblique instead of straight	
	Not to draw the curve in the bottom of the letter	
	Writing the letter oblique	
	Overhanging part in the top of the letter	
	Drawing cornered bottom tip where the curvature needs to be drawn as a curve	
	Exaggerating the curve at the bottom	

Source: Research Data

Table-16. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letter “m”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
m	No overhang in top left	
	The second line appears when the first line is crossed over the vertical line.	
	Creating a second line appearance when crossing the middle vertical line for the second time	
	Drawing vertical lines curved / oblique	
	Two curves in the letter are made in the same size	
	Distorted shape of curves in letter	
	Drawing vertical line in the middle too short	
	The lower tips of the letter are not aligned	
	To see additional places on the letter due to not paid attention to the direction of writing	

Source: Research Data

Table-17. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letter “n”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
n	No overhang in top left	
	The second line appears when the first line is crossed over the vertical line.	
	Drawing vertical lines curved / oblique	
	Drawing distorted shape of the curve in the letter	
	The lower tips of the letter are not aligned	
	There are additional places / corrections on the letter because the direction of writing is not paid attention	

Source: Research Data

Table-18. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letters “o” and “ö”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
o and ö	The formation of protrusions in the place where the drawing started, even though it started to draw from the right place	
	starting to draw from the wrong place	
	Drawing vertical/right or left curved ellipses	
	Drawing unclosed circle	
	Drawing improper circle	

Source: Research Data

Table-19. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the top part of letter “ö”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
The top part of letter “ö”	Drawing the top parts of the letter in a different alignment	
	The upper parts are too far/too close to each other	
	The top parts are too long	
	Round / dot shape of the upper parts	
	Drawing the top parts in a different size	
	Drawing the top parts at high level	

Source: Research Data

Table-20. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letter “p”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
p	No top bulge of the letter	
	Drawing the top bulge very long	
	Drawing a ribbed circle	
	Distorted drawing of round shape	
	Drawing the round part of the letter incompletely	
	Merging vertical line and rounding from the wrong place/appearing disproportionately	
	Drawing the vertical line/ the letter oblique	
	Drawing the vertical line oblique	

Source: Research Data

Table-21. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letter “r”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
r	Absence of the top bulge	
	Drawing the vertical line too long	
	Incorrect positioning of the curve part	
	Drawing the curve part short	
	Drawing the curve line as a vertical line	
	Drawing curve part upward/downward sloping	
	Drawing several times over the top of the line	

Source: Research Data

Table-22. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letters “s” and “ş”

Letters	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
s and ş	No folding at the top and / or bottom tip	
	When the curves are not properly formed / the curve needs to be drawn as a curve, drawing a sharp / angular curve	
	When the size of top and bottom parts need to be the same size, drawing the top or the bottom part bigger	
	Drawing the size of letter too high	
	Writing the letter oblique	
	Writing the letter reversely	

Source: Research Data

Table-23. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the bottom part of letter “ş”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
The bottom part of letter “ş”	Drawing the bottom part of the letter too long	
	Drawing a dot at the bottom part of the letter	
	Making the bottom part too low	
	Making the bottom part curved	
	The bottom part is not centered (left bottom/right bottom)	
	The bottom part touches the letter and / or is in the letter	

Source: Research Data

Table-24. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letter “t”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
t	Drawing the vertical line oblique	
	Placing the horizontal line at a lower position or in the middle	
	Placing the horizontal line too high or at the top	
	No fold at the bottom	
	Excessive fold at the bottom	
	The height is too short compared to the other letters (mostly)	
	Left or right tilting	
	Drawing the bottom cornered	
	To be over it because the direction of writing is not followed	

Source: Research Data

Table-25. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letters “u” and “ü”

Letters	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
u and ü	Excess output on the bottom right	
	Letter is tilted	
	No bulge at the bottom of the letter	
	Drawing the two top tips unequal	
	Drawing a distorted /an angular curve	
	Not to follow drawing directions of the letter/Drawing over and over on the same line	
	Creating a second line as passing over the same line	

Source: Research Data

Table-26. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the top part of letter “ü”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
The top part of letter “ü”	The top parts are not aligned (one is above, the other is below)	
	Upper parts are on top right / left	
	Drawing the top parts too long	
	Drawing the top parts as dots	
	The upper parts are too far or too close to each other/not in line with each other	
	One of the upper pieces and/or two of them forming a curve	
	Making one of the top parts big and the other one small	
	Making adjacent to the lower part of the upper parts	
	Drawing the top parts round	

Source: Research Data

Table-27. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letter “v”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
v	Drawing the two lines of the letter long and very close to each other	
	The top tips are too far to each other	
	Making the bottom corner ribbed	
	Making one of tips long and the other one short	
	Both of the diagonal lines need to be inclined, but here, one of them is standing upright or standing close.	
	The bottom edge must be angular, but it is drawn curved	
	It needs to be a line but curve is drawn	
	The bottom tips are not integrated	

Source: Research Data

Table-28. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letter “y”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
y	Tail not folded inward	
	Drawing the one of the top tips short and the other long	
	Writing the letter oblique	
	Drawing the tail/ the tip of the tail too short/too long	
	Creating a second line appearance when crossing the line	
	The top part needs to be drawn as a curve but it is drawn as angular	

Source: Research Data

Table-29. Types of common errors and sample visuals from these errors which were made about the letter “z”

Letter	Common Error Type	The Sample Image of Error
z	Bottom/top horizontal lines are short/long	
	Diagonal lines in the bottom, top, and/or middle are curved, not straight lines	
	The top and bottom lines are not parallel to each other or to the floor.	
	The upper right corner and/or lower left corner are lack of being sharp	
	Writing the letter like number 2	
	Placing a horizontal line in the middle of the letter	

Source: Research Data

4. Discussion

According to the findings obtained from the research, there are many types of errors related to the writing of uppercase and lowercase letters of first grade students. Mistakes about the steps of drawing followed while drawing the letter and mistakes made about the stages of drawing, in other words, typically visual mistakes are the types of error. However, it was observed that some perceptual errors related to the letters also generate to these types of errors. For example, it was observed that most of the students perceived lowercase “j” as an uppercase “J” while writing the lowercase “j” and they wrote the lowercase letter in a capital letter size. Again, it was observed that most of the students drew the lowercase j’s tail on the right side instead of drawing to the left side. Similarly, when the writing patterns of the lowercase “t” letter were analyzed, it has been observed that many students also drew the letter in the size of letters “e, n, u” without the upper extension or the lower extension. These examples are thought to be due to the fact that the students have a perceptual error in relation to these letters. When figurative mistakes are considered, it has been observed that the error type available for each letter differs according to the features and shapes of the parts required to form the letter.

In most of the letters there are places where a straight line needs to be used. Considering the situation, it has often been observed that the lines were drawn obliquely where a straight line must be used. When this is the case, the fact that the letters that must be written as vertical letters are mostly written in italic letters constitutes a proper visual to perceive in this way. It has also been observed that these parts which should be drawn as straight lines, in other words linear, are drawn as a curve at the level that is often expressed. This is one of the reasons why the letter is typed. Most of the letters have short straight line inside such as a, b, d, e, f, g-ğ, h, i-i, j, k, l, m, n, p, r, t, u-ü, v, y and z.

The letters i-i, k, v and z consist of only straight lines. Considering all the typing mistakes, it was determined that the drawing mistakes of these letters were less. However, many mistakes have been found because of the fact that the straight line is drawn in italic or curve.

The letters c-ç, o-ö and s-ş consist of only curved lines. It can be said that the ratio of errors related to these letters is similar to the error rates of the letters typed with only straight lines. Although it seems more difficult to draw curvilinear lines correctly, it has been seen that the error rates in the letters with straight lines are not at a minimum because the students are forced to draw straight lines linearly or without sloping.

The letters a, b, d, e, f, g, h, j, l, m, n, p, r, t, u-ü and y contain both a straight line part and a curved line part which must be drawn in a linear way. The students must draw both the straight line and the curvilinear line correctly, in order to write the letter correctly. In other words, it can be said that double skills are required for the correct writing of these letters. Considering the situation, the following result was observed when student drawings were evaluated in general. It has been seen that most of the students made erroneous drawing while writing these letters. It has been seen that most of the mistakes were made in the process of creating both the straight line and the curvilinear line found in the letter correctly and assembling these formed parts correctly.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, priority and importance should be given to drawing practices as an important dimension of reading and writing, however, these studies should continue to be supported by the writing process. In other words, when the drawing practices are finished, it is necessary to do extra drawing activities in an integrative process rather than focusing on letter writing. The findings of the study carried out by [Altun et al. \(2014\)](#) support the integrative writing process. In addition, another important point that is considered to be important in the literacy process is the fact that studies aimed at improving the muscular memory as well as the small muscle development of the students should be added to the process. Because the most important role in the letter writing process is the person's muscle memory. Although hands, arms and eye muscles work well and effectively, muscles must be exercised correctly and adequately in order to acquire the proper habit of making a letter. It is thought, however, that writing is lagging behind reading in the first literacy teaching process. It should be noted that the continuation of the first reading in an integrated structure is an important condition in the development of the reading skills as well as the development of the writing skills. Therefore, as [Bilir \(2005\)](#) emphasized the importance of the study, it is thought that teachers should increase their writing activities instead of just focusing on reading activities.

References

- Akdemir, A.S. and A. Eyerci, 2016. Using writing templates as materials to improve writing skills in EFL classes: An experimental study. *Mersin University Faculty of Education Journal*, 12(2): 747-756. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17860/efd.94338>.
- Akyol, H., 2001. First reading and writing instruction in Turkish. Ankara: Gündüz Education and Publishing.
- Altun, S.A., O.Ş. Cetin and D.N. Bay, 2014. Teachers' views on preparatory studies for reading and writing. *Uşak University Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(1): 244-263.
- Ayık, A. and Ö. Ataş-Akdemir, 2016. The relationship between pre-service teachers' perceptions of school quality of life and school alienation. *Journal of Educational Administration in Theory and Practice*, 21(4): 429-452. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.14527/kuey.2015.016>.
- Bay, Y., 2010. Evaluation of first reading and writing instruction with voice based sentence method. *Theoretical Education*, 3(1): 164-181.
- Belet, S. and S. Yaşar, 2007. The effect of learning strategies on reading comprehension and writing skills and attitudes towards Turkish course. *Theory and Practice in Education*, 3(1): 69-86.
- Bilir, A., 2005. Teaching the characteristics of primary school students and teaching of primary reading. *Ankara University Journal of Educational Sciences Faculty*, 38(1): 87-100.
- Celenk, S., 2007. First reading-writing program and teaching. Ankara: Maya Akademi Publications.
- Demirel, M., 2006. A research on the changes in initial literacy teaching. Selcuk University Institute of Social Sciences, Master Thesis.
- Esia-Donkoh, K. and S. Baffoe, 2018. Instructional supervisory practices of headteachers and teacher motivation in public basic schools in Anomabo education circuit. *Journal of Education and e-Learning Research*, 5(1): 43-50. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.20448/journal.509.2018.51.43.50>.
- Göğüş, B., 1982. Turkish: Teacher guide; basic education schools 1, 2, 3 classes. Istanbul: National Education Press.
- Istiningsih, 2016. Character education of the most developed countries in ASEAN. *Journal of Education and e-Learning Research*, 3(1): 32-37. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.20448/journal.509/2016.3.1/509.1.32.37>.
- Kaya, Z. and A.S. Akdemir, 2016. Learning and teaching: Theories approaches and models. Ankara: Çözüm Eğitim Yayıncılık.
- Ministry of National Education, 1997. Elementary school Turkish education writing program. *Journal of Releases*, 2482: 657-755.
- MoNE, 2018. Turkish language teaching program (Primary, Secondary, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8 Grades). Ankara: MoNE Publications. pp:12.
- Sahin, A., 2012. Problems encountered in teaching oblique fonts. *Education and Science*, 37(165): 168-179.
- Stake, R.E., 1995. The art of case study research. Thousand Oaks: Sage Pbc.
- Yin, R.K., 2009. Case study methods: Design and methods. 4th Edn., Thousand Oaks: Sage Pbc.
- Yin, R.K., 2012. Applications of case study research. Thousand Oaks: Sage Pbc.